

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILL AND COMMUNICATION ABILITY OF THE STUDENTS

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Cite This Article: K. Manigandan, N. Santha Kumar & B. Devi, "The Importance of English Speaking Skill and Communication Ability of the Students", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 137-139, 2017.

Abstract:

This paper endeavors to express about the importance of English speaking skill in the modern world, and how speaking skill is been ignored by the students rather by teachers who ask the students to predominantly focus on the written skill when they are in schools and are giving more prominence to the writing skill than the speaking skill in order to get more marks in their public examinations of standard 10th and 12th which lead the students to drive to the higher studies if they secure the mandatory marks. That is why, when students enter college or university, students are struggling a lot in their higher studies while communicating to others in English. Therefore, this study discusses how English speaking skill is important in the present situation and how students can improve English speaking skill.

Introduction:

Without English language today, we cannot move our day to day life with ease in the up-to-date world. Almost across the world, the people of the globe interconnect English in their daily conversation due to official or personal reasons. The importance of English language cannot be unexploited and discarded since English language is the most common language spoken everywhere in the world. With the advent of developing technology, English has been playing a major role in the entire field. Today, almost everyone uses to speak about the standing of English language in the current world. Moreover, many mainstreams of the educational institutions have medium of English language to be taught to the students of their own institution in innumerable courses which runs by them. Even, otherwise students are not able to communicate up to the level of a company or organization expectation.

Mother Tongue Influence (MTI):

"We initially use sounds from our mother tongue and has mother tongue influence (MTI) to begin with. More and more listening to those fluent in the second language, practicing speaking yourself and correcting mistakes, you slowly learn to replace your mother tongue sounds with the original sounds of English" (A Study on Mother Tongue Influence In English Communication). Anybody can learn any language in the world, but before learning any language one must know about one's mother tongue accurately. Because, which would help one to know the basic organizations of any language. Generally, a language must have grammatical structure to frame a sentence or to communicate one to another correctly, we need the structure. Thus, most probably, almost all the languages which has written and spoken formats might be the similar basic formats merely such as Sentence pattern, voices, Tenses Etc., While learning a second language, people use to translate second language into their own language and make conversation to others. For basic learners, it can be useful whereas learner who wants to communicate fluently should not influence of your mother tongue often.

Skills:

A statement coated in the work of "Teaching of English at Primary Level in Government Schools" by Dr. Usha Dutta, NCERT & Dr. Neeru Bala, TSG - SSA, EdCIL 2012 is "Language learning is not just a matter of acquiring the skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing but it consists of developing a communicative competence where these skills are often used in an integrated manner along with several other abilities". In English language, there are four skills. They are (LSRW) L-Listening-S-Speaking R-Reading, W-Writing. All the four skills are very important, on the other hand somehow the students give importance to the written skill, is obligatory at the time of doing school/ college. That may be absolutely fine, no doubt about it. But, it helps only to achieve or get a particular task. Nonetheless, on learning any language. All the skills are very important, and one cannot specify that the particular skill is more important than the other skills.

Written Skill is given More Importance than the Speaking Skill:

In the school, students are asked to focus more on other three skills than written skill. Consequently, students may get more marks in their public examinations. However, when they enter college or university level, students are struggling to communicate in English to others, getting tensed, and it makes the students to get inferiority. If he/she feels that they are inferior to the others. The thought which they feel lead their life into dangerous situation. When they are in School, they are used to doing "Rote-learning" to get more marks, helping the students to get into their new course in college or university. Only then, the problem of speaking in English starts due to their Rote-learning. In school, syllabus is within the limitation, whereas university syllabus

would be high and are used to communicating only in English, which makes the students to face real a kind of basic concern.

Social Community:

Our life is based on community, strongly believed that learning a language should be a societal practice. Hence, placing our learning in the background of eloquent association is needed. In many schools and colleges, a kind of mechanical approach and Rote learning lead pupils to be a lack in the speaking skill. So, cultivating external motivation on English language is important. The rationale behind the lack of speaking skill is DOTT (Lack of Drive, Lack of Obligation, Lack of Technique and Lack of Thoughts). English is being emphasized by almost every person studying in Schools or Colleges. Since, it has been the most sought after language by the trade across the world. From the age of Macaulay till now, though there are a lot of changes, Maximum Regional medium students are still undeveloped and unequipped with English Language given a great value at more of all professional area. As for regional medium students' lack in English Proficiency. In the School the study is the basic concern for; the academy gives importance to the writing skill more than Speaking Skill.

Rote Learning:

Because, Students' skill is being valued only through written examination. Consequently, the rote learning originates and gains the ground due to the lack of English language of the students studying at Tamil Medium. By this rationale, Students miss getting influence in Listening, Reading and Speaking. So, by default, 'the students are molded in order to get better percentage than the Skill needed' to survive in this current corporate world. In Many schools, Students are being forced to write in English before they have enough quittances in English language, which makes the students to go with the rote learning. Technically speaking, the techniques in English learning are not taught in many schools, but the rote learning. Hence, to break the rote learning, each of the students should understand the techniques in English Language and about the methods lie in the English learning.

Cognitive Theory:

The learning in cognitive theory determines the procurement, aware and rational intellectual process, connecting the careful practise of scholarship strategies. It is the distinct means of giving out material that increase grasps in English language. The learning in cognitive theory determines the procurement, aware and rational intellectual process, connecting the careful practise of scholarship strategies. It is the distinct means of giving out material that increases grasp in English language. For regional medium schools, there should be occupational opportunities through English teaching. Even University Grants Commission has declared English as vocational Subject since It has become international trade language. So, Aim, Objective, content, and instructional aspect should be revised based on this corporate world English. Only then Regional medium students can get a kind of reverent job in this competitive world.

Vedic Days:

In Vedic days, Teaching was oral, it is said that all had understood and proved their Excellency. But, in this modern era, it becomes tough, why? There is no time based teaching and learning material. Majority of the schools, students are taught English only to get marks, but not about to be competitive to this competitive world. We need such a material which is cognitive English learning material.

Problem Other Than Educational Area:

Environment:

The first cause is that makes the students difficult in speaking English is that the environment does not support the students to speak English frequently. The environment here means the people outside the class. Those people may think that the students just want to show off when they speak English for daily conversation. The response that the students get makes them loose their self-confidence to improve their speaking. Since the students do not want to be rejected by the people around them, so they use their native language in daily conversation. That makes the students unable to communicate in English fluently outside the class.

Grammar:

In many vernacular medium schools, teacher gives the important questions and answers to the students for their examination purpose. And for grammar section, it becomes negligible, since it has been with sets of rules. Even though there are new methods in English language and teaching, still vernacular medium students are getting struggled to get accuracy and fluency in English language. Moreover, there are singular and plural forms that the students have to distinguish and still many forms that have to be learned. Most students are very easy to get confused with English grammar, while grammar is very needed to form a right sentence. If the students do not have grammar mastery, of course they will not be able to produce sentences that grammatically right. Realizing that the grammar, students have is very weak, so they feel embarrassed when they want to produce English sentences orally. Now, English is an international language. Even technology and working world use English. It is believed that the students want to be the winner in working world competition that is getting tight day by day. One of the conditions that the students must require is having ability to speak English

fluently. This skill will be their plus point in facing the working world. From now on, the students have to try hard to overcome their difficulties to speak English fluently.

Methods and Techniques to be Adapted to Improve Speaking Skill:

Associating technique with cognitive approach might be a great use among the Tamil medium students. It can be like Trial and error play in speaking skill. If one knows how to make a clean sentence in English, he/she can be an error analyst, and they can make their own sentences without errors. While comparing the sentences, One's brain captures and remembers the ideology of making and associating the sentences. And, it can be empowering the mind power of comprehending one's understand ability.

Need of English Language:

Be it media. Journals, corporate company and so on, English language is specific. Whereas, its reach should be reached by the regional medium school children as well. For that, cognitive test should be carried out through practical English classes.

Motivation:

As described by Little wood, (1984: 53) 'Motivation is the crucial force which determines whether a learner embarks in a task at all, how much energy he/she devotes to it, and how long he/she perseveres.'. A motivation is a self-drive and self determination to achieve a task or learn a language or an art. In order to motivate a person to take up the task which seems to be impossible due to its unfamiliarity or lack of scope of learning. Hence, in order to motivate a person to learn a new thing requires counselling and make them understand nothing is impossible if constantly tried and provide them suitable platform and opportunities to gain confidence.

Bridge Course:

A connection that joins two different level medium and curriculum students into one. Generally, many colleges do not conduct Bridge course, but it should be conducted every year. Because, when the school students enter first year in a University/College they ought to know the syllabus or curriculum which will be taught in their new course for which the Bridge course is important it makes the students to connect one to another.

Orientation- Sequencer:

A sequencer which gives information about the field or subjects to newcomers who joins a university or other institution. The students whoever joins newly an organization must organise orientation programme, which will be helpful for them to know about their field and it will guide them to know how to deal or handle the situation correctly.

Communication Workshop:

Communication is an important one in our life. In a company or an organization, a person who makes clear communication will be appreciated and respected known by others knowingly or unknowingly, and the reason behind is communicative skill which they have. OF late, an organization or institution organizes communication- workshop where they may able to overcome whatever problem faced by them communicating to others in English.

Conclusion:

In the level of school itself, one must know the basic i.e., four skills. Only then, they can flourish the field they are in. It would be of help to one when one enters college/university. Because, school is a place where good thing can be taught and teacher and the management of the regional medium schools have to focus on all the four skills, are important, especially "the speaking skill". A survey says ie, in an interview, if 100 students are attending, only ten to twenty students are speaking correctly and getting placed. Whereas, others are not up to the standard to what the company or organization expects, due to giving more importance on the written skill when they are in schools. Therefore, a student can focus on all the four skills and a little more concentration can be put on the speaking skill. Whatever points we discussed in the above paragraphs could be followed to get fluent in English Speaking skill.

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